

Leverage, Corporate Philanthropy and Institutional Environment: Evidence from China

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Abstract

Based on the perspective of institutional theory and resource-based theory, this study examines the relationship between leverage and the amount of corporate donation. Also, we explore whether this relation is influenced by institutional environment. Using empirical data from China, a typical emerging market, we find that for state-owned enterprises (SOEs), there is a negative relationship between leverage and donation amount, while this association turns to positive for non-SOEs. We suggest this difference is caused by China's institutional environment. Since non-SOEs are lack of endorsement, they are more likely to do corporate philanthropy to build a close link with the government, while SOEs needn't do this because they can get enough support from the government even they don't do corporate philanthropy. This result indicates that institutional environment makes the strategy of corporate philanthropy of SOEs different from the behavior pattern of non-SOEs.

Keywords Leverage; Corporate Philanthropy; Corporate Social Responsibility; Institutional Environment; Emerging Markets; China

Introduction

In recent years, a growing body of literature has shed light on the issue of corporate philanthropy which is regarded as a prominent component of Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR). Prior studies (Adams and Hardwick 1998, Amato and Amato 2007, Waddock and Graves 1997, Wang and Coffey 1992, Ortiz-de-Mandojana et al. 2014), investigating the determinants of corporate philanthropy, focus on the link between firm size, the composition of the board, ownership structure as well as resource slack and Corporate Philanthropy. However, leverage, a significant part of the financial capital structure, receives little academic attention. Further, although it is noted that CSR behavior would be affected by the institutional environment (Campbell 2007), the relevant empirical evidence is few. Does leverage affect corporate philanthropy? Does the institutional environment of emerging markets complicate the relationship between the above two? In order to answer the questions above, drawing on the perspective of institutional theory and resource-based theory, our study examines the relationship between leverage and the amount of corporate donation in the context of the biggest emerging market, China.

Given that, as a core content of China's institutional environment, the state-owned enterprises (SOEs) controlled by the government ultimately, play a more influential role in the market than their counterparts, we analyze the corporate philanthropy initiatives of SOEs apart from the rest of firms and attempt to explain the difference of corporate philanthropy between SOEs and non-SOEs. Using the data of China's listed companies from 2008 to 2012, we find that consistent with prior studies (Adams and Hardwick 1998, Brown et al. 2006, Ducassy 2013) root in developed countries, leverage of SOEs is associated with the donation amount in a negative way, however, for the non-SOEs, the relation is positive. We attribute the reversed relations to the institutional environment in China and in emerging markets in general. Finally, in order to confirm the robustness of the outcome, we test the results by an alternative proxy, based on the theory of resource slack.

This paper contributes to the literature in several ways. First, to the best knowledge of ours, this is the first study to directly examine the relationship between leverage and corporate philanthropy based on the context of emerging market. Although the influence of leverage on corporate performance has been documented by

prior studies (Opler and Titman 1994, Lang et al. 1996, Pushner 1995, González 2013), we extend the literature to a significant component of corporate performance, namely, corporate philanthropy performance which is regarded as a prominent element of CSR (Brammer and Millington 2008). Second, although those corporate social behaviors are affected by institutional environment has been identified by theoretical studies (Campbell, 2007, Matten and Moon, 2008), it is lack of empirical evidence. China, the biggest emerging country and transition economy in the world, provides us a unique opportunity to investigate the motivation of corporate philanthropy empirically. Finally, the empirical results and the findings might suggest lessons to the countries where SOEs are still dominant, such as Singapore, Malaysia, Austria, and Finland (Claessens et al. 2000, Faccio and Lang 2002) and where the government is really influential to the market.

Literature review and hypotheses development

Literature review

The potential impact of leverage on firm performance varies across different definitions of performance and countries. By employing market share and market value of equity as the proxies of company performance on the samples of US firms, Opler and Titman (1994) find that due to the cost of financial distress, during downturns, the performance of firms with high leverage are more likely to decline in both sales and value of equity. Similarly, Pushner (1995) also suggests a negative relationship between leverage and corporate performance which is measured by total factor productivity. Later, Weill (2007) advances prior studies by including the effect of institutional environment. Particularly, Weill (2007) finds that the relationship between leverage and corporate performance varies across countries and he contributes this phenomenon to the influence of institutional factor. More recently, by using the data from different legal origin countries, González (2013) points out that although much evidence indicates the predominance of financial distress costs over the benefits of debt, the relations can be reversed in the regions where the protection towards shareholder rights and the system of legal enforcement are weak.

Taken together, these empirical studies contribute to the debate on leverage and firm performance, focusing on the definition of firm performance and institutional environment that are associated with leverage. However, on the one hand, although a variety of firm performance has been examined by prior studies, CSR performance, as an important part of the firm performance, is largely ignored. On the other hand, given that institutional structure determines CSR (Jones 1999), the difference on the institutional environment between developed countries and developing countries is likely to impact the CSR practice. The prior research mainly pays attention to the firms in developed markets, empirical studies on the samples of emerging countries are rare (Li and Zhang 2010).

Although prior literature explores the relationship between leverage and corporate philanthropy, the studies employing leverage as an explanatory variable are few, and the results are mixed. This can be explained by two main factors. First, following the argument of prior research based on institutional theory (Campbell 2007, Matten and Moon 2008, Ioannou and Serafeim 2012), institutional environment matters in the determination of CSR, without a full analysis of China's institutional environment, prior studies probably miss important element affecting corporate philanthropy. Second, given the limitation of data available, previous studies only examine the association by using the data of a specific event (e.g., Zhang et al. 2009) or the data collected within one year (e.g., Li and Zhang 2010), which limit the reliability of their results. Using the sample of manufacturing firms in China during the past five years, we extend the existing literature on the link between leverage and corporate philanthropy, as well as the impact of the institutional environment.

Hypotheses development

The primary objective of this study is to provide evidence on the relationship between leverage and philanthropy, and the influence of institutional environment. Because of the direct cost and indirect cost

(González 2013), it is widely accepted that high financial leverage leads to the reduction of financial resource that could be spent on CSR instead. Although the effect of direct cost, including the expense for lawyer, accountant, and interest for the debt, is not so great, as estimated by Altman and Hotchkiss (2010), the direct cost holds 8.1% (median 2%) of pre-bankruptcy assets on average for a sample of 225 smaller firms. The indirect cost, including the inability to access to the profitable project for the financial resource limitation (Cheng et al. 2014), or lost market share due to the deteriorating financial condition (Opler and Titman 1994) and distracting the management attention (González 2013), is identified to occupy the precious resources of firm and then to inflict the firm performance finally. Further, by surveying 241 corporate executives, Aupperle et al (1985) estimate the relevant relative degrees of importance on each obligation the firm need to fulfill and the results indicate that the relative importance of economic equals to 3.5, legal equals to 2.54, ethical equals to 2.22, and discretionary is the least important from the perspective of corporate executives as 1.30.

However, compared with their counterparts in developed countries, the firms in China face a really different institutional environment which leads to distinct corporate philanthropy patterns between SOEs and non-SOEs. First, differ from the companies in developed areas, the dominant element of China's public listed companies are SOEs. As it is documented by Faccio and Lang (2002), the ratio of SOEs in the UK is 0.08%, 6.30% in Germany and 5.11% in France, while in China, this ratio is as high as 63.25% (Li and Zhang 2010). Given that the SOEs constitute a sizeable proportion of Chinese public listed companies, the competitive advantage and the monopolistic status of SOEs would surely affect the survival of non-SOEs. Furthermore, the government, as the back of SOEs, is much more influential than its counterparts in western countries (Liu 2006). The government allows SOEs to have a big advantage in access to various resources. For example, Wang et al. (2008) suggest that compared with non-SOEs, SOEs are more likely to receive financial insurance and government bailout when they have financial problems. Besides, it is possible that the state-owned banks provide finance to SOEs because of political connections rather than profitability (Chen et al. 2010). Hence, in order to survive and adapt to the institutional environment, non-SOEs tend to adopt different corporate philanthropy strategy.

It has been widely documented that corporate philanthropy practice has become increasingly merged into the firm strategy which meets the requirement of key stakeholders, such as the government in the context of China, and finally enhances the corporate performance and company value in return. (Neiheisel 1994, Sánchez 2000, Zhang et al. 2009). Saiia et al. (2003) defines strategic philanthropy as the "giving of corporate resources to address non-business community issues that also benefit the firm's strategic position, and ultimately, its bottom line." Facing the financial stress and risk of bankruptcy caused by high leverage, different firms tend to drop into different corporate philanthropy practice to build its own strategy. For SOEs, in order to make sure their business run smoothly, it's reasonable to reduce the degree of corporate philanthropy and remove the saved financial resource to daily operation circle. However, non-SOEs are more likely to choose a reversed way to fulfill corporate philanthropy strategy for several reasons. First, prior studies have indicated that the companies with superior CSR performance are more likely to disclose the CSR information through CSR reporting (Dhaliwal et al. 2011) and consequently leading to better access to finance as returns (Cheng et al. 2014). Therefore, in order to avoid bankruptcy and reduce the degree of financial stress, non-SOEs, unlike SOEs having easier access to bank loan due to their governmental background (Brandt and Li 2003, Ferri and Liu 2010), tend to spend more on corporate philanthropy to reduce financial constraints. Second, given that the companies with political connection are more likely to gain financial assistance from the government (Faccio et al. 2006), and it has also been evidenced that in the context of China, there is a positive relationship between corporate philanthropy and political connection (Li et al. 2014), we conjecture non-SOEs are motivated to build a political connection to enhance the possibility

of being bailed out by the risk of bankruptcy. Finally, prior studies indicate that CSR practice helps firms build a good reputation and indirectly improve the financial performance (Surroca et al. 2010, Michelon et al. 2013), which finally loosens the financial stress. In order to reduce the risk ultimately, we propose that the managers in non-SOEs tend to invest more in corporate philanthropy as its unique strategy. Consequently, we propose the two hypotheses.

H1: There is a negative relationship between leverage and the amount of corporate philanthropy for SOEs.

H2: There is a positive relationship between leverage and the amount of corporate philanthropy for non-SOEs.

Research methods-Sample

We base our empirical test on the sample of China's listed companies in Shenzhen Stock Exchange and Shanghai Stock Exchange, over the period 2008–2012. Given that CSR practice varies across industries (Beliveau et al. 1994), following the prior studies (Li and Zhang 2010), we narrow the sample to the manufacturing sector of the industry. The data of finance and ownership is sourced from the China Stock Market and Accounting Research (CSMAR) database which is widely used by scholars for Chinese listed firms (Li et al. 2014). The data of donation amount is collected from CSR reports of China's listed companies, which is also provided by CSMAR. Although at the beginning we have more than 500 observations, around 10% of the sample is lost for the missing of ownership and financial data. Finally, we end up with 461 observations, including 261 for SOEs and 200 for non-SOEs.

Multivariate Analysis

We employ the following regression to examine the relationship between leverage and corporate philanthropy, for both of SOEs and non-SOEs, after controlling other factors.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Donation} = & \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{Lev} + \beta_2 \text{Sales} + \beta_3 \text{Assets} + \beta_4 \text{Employees} \\ & + \beta_5 Q + \beta_6 \text{Profit} + \beta_7 \text{Ins_owner} + \sum \text{Year} + \varepsilon \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

The definitions of the variables in the equation are as follows.

Dependent Variable

It has been stated that the amount of corporate donation implicates a firm's philanthropic contributions (Li et al. 2014), following the research of Zhang et al. (2009), we employ Donation amount (in ten thousand RMB) as the proxy of corporate philanthropy.

Independent Variable

In common with earlier contributions (Li and Zhang 2010), the *Lev1* that we employ equal to the ratio of total liability divided by the total asset. In order to make sure our results are robust, following previous literature (Brammer and Millington 2008, Dou et al. 2014), we also employ the ratio of total liability to equity as *Lev2*.

Control Variables

Consistent with prior studies, we employ a set of control variables as follows. Although various firm attributes are documented to affect CSR, firm size is identified as a vital factor (Madden et al. 2006, Udayasankar 2008), which does not only bring resource slack, driving firms toward CSR but bring public pressure to firms as well (Brammer and Millington 2006). Given the definitions of firm size are not conformity, in order to fully control the impact of resource slack and visibility, following existing studies (Waddock and Graves 1997, Elsayed 2006, Amato and Amato 2012, Sánchez et al. 2011), we employ *Assets* (log form of total assets), *Sales* (sales amount in ten million RMB) and *Employees* (the number of employees, in ten thousand) as proxies of firm size. Moreover, in order to capture the opportunities of corporate future alternative investment which could be spent on corporate giving, following prior studies (Li and Zhang 2010), we employ *Tobin's Q* (sum of marketing value and debt value divided by total assets

without the net value of goodwill and intangible assets). Except for firm size and Tobin's Q, financial performance has been widely accepted (McElroy and Siegfried 1985, Julian and Ofori-dankwa 2013) to have effects on the CSR performance. Thus, we also employ *Profit* (net profit, in ten million RMB) as a control variable. Finally, Wahba (2008, 2010) suggest institutional investors are associated with corporate environmental performance. Therefore, *Ins_owner* (the shareholding of institutional investors) is included to cover the effect of corporate governance.

Empirical results

We provide the descriptive statistics of donation and financial characteristics for 461 listed firms, as well as a comparison of those characteristics between state-owned and non-state-owned firms in Table 1. The average donation amount is 4,884 thousand RMB on the sample of full, and we do not find a significant difference between SOEs and non-SOEs. The leverage of SOEs is significantly ($p < 0.01$, for both of Lev1 and Lev2) higher than non-SOEs, which is consistent with our analysis that, compared with non-SOEs, SOEs are easier to access to a financial resource. Thus SOEs are more likely to have high leverage. Total assets, sales amount and number of employees of SOEs are significantly larger than those of non-SOEs, indicating the difference of operational scale between them. Consistent with prior studies (Li and Zhang 2010), the descriptive statistics also indicate SOEs have a significant lower Tobin's Q than non-SOEs do, while no significant difference of institutional ownership has been found between the two groups. Finally, SOEs have a better financial performance than non-SOEs.

Table 1 Descriptive statistics

Variables	Mean (full)	Standard Deviation	Mean (non-SOE)	Mean (SOE)	MeanDiff
Donation	488.492	1,140.200	404.576	552.794	-148.218
Lev1	0.460	0.196	0.375	0.526	-0.151***
Lev2	1.169	0.983	0.770	1.474	-0.704***
Sales	1,340.378	1,934.858	570.576	1,930.265	-1360***
Assets	22.670	1.308	21.992	23.190	-1.198***
Employees	10.565	12.357	6.439	13.727	-7.288***
Q	2.262	1.636	2.435	2.130	0.305**
Ins_owner	0.095	0.115	0.077	0.108	-0.031***
Profit	76.814	111.244	46.847	99.777	-52.930***

* $p < 0.1$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$

Regression results

We present the results of multiple regression analysis in Table 2 and Table 3. With the regard of independent variables, the parameters of Lev1 and Lev2 are consistent with the hypotheses as we provide. Specifically, Table 2 indicates that there is a negative relationship between leverage and donation amount on the sample of SOEs, while this association reversed for the firms of non-SOEs. This relationship is significant at $p=0.05$. Besides, by employing an alternative proxy, we gain a similar result as exhibited in Table 3. Therefore, it is reasonable to accept the hypotheses that for SOEs, the financial stress brought by leverage, influences the amount of corporate donation negatively, while non-SOEs facing the lack of financial resource are in an entirely different pattern. They are motivated to spend more on the corporate philanthropy because of the institutional environment.

Consistent with previous studies (Adams and Hardwick 1998), profit is positively correlated with donation amount for both SOEs and non-SOEs, suggesting that no matter for SOEs or non-SOEs, the corporate philanthropy is always constrained by financial resource available. Besides, some of the other variables of firms' characteristics are also significant. For example, for SOEs, total assets is indicated to promote

corporate philanthropy consistently, while for non-SOEs, Tobin's Q is revealed to play a significant role in motivating firms towards corporate philanthropy. Finally, it is interesting to notice that, for non-SOEs, the number of employees is associated with donation amount negatively. Given that non-SOEs are under the pressure of the government (Zhang et al. 2009), the results in the tables appear that the more employees non-SOEs hire, the more bargain chips they hold to against the philanthropy requirement from the government.

Table 2 Multiple regression results for tests of the relation between the amounts of donation and Lev1 in each group

Variables	Full Sample	SOEs	non-SOEs
<i>Lev1</i>	-163.3 (-0.44)	-1377.4** (-2.57)	1207.9** (2.36)
<i>Sales</i>	-0.105** (-2.16)	-0.0965 (-1.60)	-0.123 (-1.08)
<i>Assets</i>	192.8** (2.41)	343.5*** (2.91)	-14.84 (-0.13)
<i>Employees</i>	13.24* (1.82)	8.300 (0.96)	-37.31** (-2.00)
<i>Q</i>	140.6*** (3.64)	88.70 (1.64)	129.3** (2.33)
<i>Ins_owner</i>	180.2 (0.42)	158.6 (0.31)	-260.7 (-0.31)
<i>Profit</i>	2.757*** (4.51)	1.733** (2.46)	12.45*** (5.70)
<i>Intercept</i>	-3884.1** (-2.33)	-6234.6** (-2.47)	-244.2 (-0.11)
Year	Yes	Yes	Yes
N	461	261	200
Adj. R ²	0.17	0.16	0.29

* p < 0.1, ** p < 0.05, *** p < 0.01

Table 3 Multiple regression results for tests of the relation between the amounts of donation and Lev2 in each group

Variables	Full Sample	SOEs	non-SOEs
<i>Lev2</i>	-49.70 (-0.73)	-144.6* (-1.82)	332.9** (2.28)
<i>Sales</i>	-0.101** (-2.06)	-0.0976 (-1.61)	-0.141 (-1.20)
<i>Assets</i>	199.4*** (2.61)	293.7** (2.54)	0.180 (0.00)
<i>Employees</i>	13.00* (1.79)	9.825 (1.13)	-37.75** (-2.02)
<i>Q</i>	140.8*** (3.78)	124.8** (2.43)	124.6** (2.26)
<i>Ins_owner</i>	170.0 (0.40)	172.9 (0.33)	-181.4 (-0.21)
<i>Profit</i>	2.691***	1.804**	12.54***

	(4.34)	(2.51)	(5.71)
<i>Intercept</i>	-4048.2**	-5721.3**	-346.5
	(-2.47)	(-2.24)	(-0.15)
<i>Year</i>	Yes	Yes	Yes
N	461	261	200
Adj. R ²	0.17	0.15	0.29

* p < 0.1, ** p < 0.05, *** p < 0.01

Further analysis

Although leverage implies the shortage of financial resource available, it also indicates that firms have good credit. It has been documented that leverage is not only identified as the proxy of financial stress but also a measurement of potential resource slack (Daniel et al. 2004). For SOEs, we propose that SOEs with good credit are not motivated to invest more in corporate philanthropy, because they concern more about the financial stress, rather than how to maintain the high credit since their government background naturally brings them credit. However, for non-SOEs, on the one hand, good credit is a consequence of their corporate philanthropy practice. Therefore, the relationship between credit and corporate philanthropy should be positive. On the other hand, firms with good credit can attract more attention from stakeholders. Thus they are likely to spend more on corporate philanthropy. In sum, based on the perspective of potential resource slack, the difference between SOEs and non-SOEs still remain.

In order to fully investigate the impact of potential resource slack on corporate philanthropy, except the leverage we employ in the main test, following the prior research (Daniel et al. 2004, Hoskisson and Johnson 1992), we rework the previous regression by employing Lev3 (debt to sales) as independent variables and the results are presented in Table 4 and finally, we obtain similar results as shown in Table 2 and Table 3.

Table 4 Multiple regression results for tests of the relation between the amounts of donation and Lev3 in each group

Variables	Full Sample	SOEs	non-SOEs
<i>Lev3</i>	-55.17 (-0.43)	-326.4** (-2.00)	548.5*** (2.80)
<i>Sales</i>	-0.117** (-2.22)	-0.164** (-2.47)	0.0561 (0.49)
<i>Assets</i>	190.6** (2.46)	313.1*** (2.65)	-21.37 (-0.20)
<i>Employees</i>	13.86* (1.93)	12.94 (1.51)	-41.92** (-2.26)
<i>Q</i>	142.3*** (3.79)	120.0** (2.33)	127.6** (2.35)
<i>Ins_owner</i>	182.0 (0.43)	230.9 (0.45)	-215.8 (-0.26)
<i>Profit</i>	2.806*** (4.70)	2.119*** (3.08)	11.40*** (5.33)
<i>Intercept</i>	-3880.5** (-2.33)	-6132.3** (-2.37)	75.39 (0.03)
<i>Year</i>	Yes	Yes	Yes
N	461	261	200
Adj. R ²	0.17	0.16	0.30

* $p < 0.1$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$

Discussion and Conclusions

The purpose of this research is to extend the understanding of the antecedent of CSR in general and the influence of leverage on corporate philanthropy in the context of China's unique institutional environment, in particular. Although it has been documented that leverage affects the corporate operational performance through bringing financial stress, the impact on CSR is ignored to a large extent, and the works root in the context of developing countries are rare. The empirical evidence we find suggests that for SOEs, there is a negative relationship between leverage and donation amount, which is consistent with prior studies on the sample of developed countries (Adams and Hardwick, 1998, Brown et al., 2006). In the meantime, this association turns to positive on the sample of non-SOEs, which is attributed to China's institutional environment. Compared with SOEs, non-SOEs are lack of endorsement from the government which controls a vast of resource in China, therefore, facing financial stress caused by high leverage, non-SOEs tend to invest more in corporate philanthropy to build a good relationship with the government and consequently, obtain easier access to the various resource. Moreover, the high leverage not only causes financial stress but also indicates a great credit from the perspective of potential resource slack. Thus, we employ an alternative proxy for potential resource slack, and finally, the results remain valid. Here it is reasonable to draw the conclusion that the political influence of government, as well as the institutional environment, makes the strategy of corporate philanthropy of SOEs different from the behavior pattern of non-SOEs.

In addition to enriching the academic literature, this study also has several implications for the policymakers and practitioners as well. First, our work reveals that, due to the influence of government, non-SOEs are motivated to engage in corporate philanthropy even under the deteriorating financial condition. This indicates the government as a powerful stakeholder could erode the interest of other stakeholders, such as the loaner and the unbalanced relationship among stakeholders could damage the value of firm finally (Benson and Davidson 2010). While for SOEs, the bounties from the government prevent them from using resource efficiently and consequently reduce the benefit of all the stakeholders at last. Therefore, for the government and policymakers, it is important to notice that in order to build a fair market environment and an efficient mechanism for the collection and distribution of resource, they need to further reduce their influence on the firms and industry sectors. Second, our evidenced association between leverage and corporate giving also provides implications to the managers in SOEs and non-SOEs. For managers in SOEs, our work suggests them to integrate corporate philanthropy into business strategy to enhance the management of stakeholders and to obtain better financial performance. For non-SOEs, our findings highlight the risk which is generated by investing in corporate philanthropy while under high leverage.

Although this study explores the understanding of leverage, corporate philanthropy, and institutional environment, there are still several open issues worthy of exploring, suggesting some directions for future research. First, our empirical results show that although the impact of leverage on corporate giving varies across different types of ownership, the influence of profit is consistently positive and significant. A possible explanation is that although the managers of non-SOEs tend to take the risk under high leverage, they are also sensitive to the shortage of resource available and cautious about the spending on corporate giving even facing the pressure of political influence and the lure of the resource from the government. According to the theory of resource slack, profit indicates the level of resource available, while leverage shows the degree of the potential resource. Therefore, the different influence between resource available and potential resource on the corporate philanthropy provides opportunities for future research. Second, our study uses the donation amount, disclosing by China's listed companies, which has two limitations. First, donation amount just captures one aspect of corporate philanthropy and CSR performance. Thus, it is a research direction to employ a more comprehensive dataset to depict a multidimensional picture of corporate philanthropy.

Second, due to the limitation of data available, we employ the data from China's firms only. It is possible that our findings are specific to the environment of China and not to the developing countries in general. Hence, a study, employing a more broad-based dataset or comparative research with multinational data would extend the knowledge of corporate philanthropy.

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